

stages (76 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and the flag leaf (LAD1) or second leaf (LAD2) were observed. At all growth stages, incidence on all upper three leaves (ILT) was closely related to average severity on these leaves (ALAD).

Results suggest that BB severity can be assessed on one of the upper three leaves instead of on all three. The method could be further simplified by counting infected leaves, rather than by estimating leaf damage. □

Susceptibility of bacterial blight (BB) differential varieties of IRRI, Japan, and Korea in Nepal

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Xco) is a major rice disease in the terai and inner terai regions (main rice-growing area) of Nepal. Recently, this disease was observed also in the warm river basins of the hill regions. The numerous pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal hinder efforts to breed resistant varieties. To identify pathogenic variability of Xco, IRRI and Japanese varieties were tested as possible differentials at Parwanipur, Janakpur, and Kankai from 1979 to 1987.

Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of differential varieties were transplanted in 3 rows, each 5 m long. Each hill had 1 seedling and spacing was 20 × 20 cm. The plots were fertilized with NPK at 120-30-30 kg/ha. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering. The disease was scored 21 d after inoculation according to the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All IRRI varieties and Japanese differentials except DV85 in the 1979 test at Kankai were found susceptible to Nepalese isolates. The differential varieties have these resistance genes: Java 14, *Xa-1* and *Xa-3*; Kogyoku, *Xa-1* and *Xa-kg*; Nigeria 5, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; Tetep, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; IR20, *Xa-4*; IR1545-339-2-2, *xa-5*; DV85, *xa-5* and

Xa-7 Kuntlan, *Xa-6*; and CAS209, *Xa-10*. During 1979 tests, Korean differentials Milyang 23, Yushin, Suweon 281, and Tongil with resistance genes from Kinmaze, Kogyoku, Kogyoku, and Rantai-emas groups, respectively, were also nonfunctional against Parwanipur and Kankai isolates.

Thus, IRRI, Japanese, and Korean resistant varieties cannot be used as differentials to identify pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal. Therefore, national programs should develop their own differentials, possibly using local popular varieties, to monitor pathogenic variability of Xco. □

Insect resistance

Use of tissue culture to evaluate rice resistance to lepidopterous pests

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Larval development was evaluated on plant tissues cultured from rice genotypes varying in levels of insect resistance. Murashige and Skoog (MS) and Linsmaier and Skoog (LS) media were used to induce and develop callus. Each liter of MS medium was supplemented with 2 mg 2, 4-D, 1 mg BAP, and 30 g sucrose (MS3); and each

liter of LS medium, with 1 mg 2,4-D and 30 g sucrose. *Oryza ridleyi* and Rexoro calli were obtained on LS medium; Chianan 2, Yabami Montakhab 47, and IR5865-26-1 calli were obtained on MS3 medium.

In a no-choice bioassay, about 200 mg of callus were placed in a 5-cm-diameter Gelman 7242 petri dish (see figure). Rexoro and *O. ridleyi* were susceptible and resistant checks, respectively. Due to limitations in available callus, Chianan 2 was bioassayed only against *Scirpophaga incertulas*, Yabami Montakhab 47 against *Chilo suppressalis*, and Ptb 10 and IR5865-26-1 against *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Insect egg masses were surface sterilized and incubated at 28 °C until eggs hatched. Callus in each petri

Lepidopterous pests reared on rice plant calli: a) *C. medinalis* larvae feeding on Ptb 10 callus; b) *S. incertulas* larva feeding on resistant *O. ridleyi* callus; c) growth of *C. medinalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (c1), IR5865-26-1 (c2), Ptb 10 (c3), and Rexoro (c4); and d) growth of *C. suppressalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (d1), Yabami Montakhab 47 (d2), and Rexoro (d3). IRRI, 1987-88.